

MULTI-FUNCTIONAL PROPERTIES IN NATURAL FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Natural fiber composites, Thermal conductivity, Fiber content, Lumen

ABSTRACT

A composite unit cell model is developed to estimate the effective transverse thermal conductivity of unidirectional green composites (K) based on a thermal-electrical analogy technique. The effective transverse thermal conductivity K is found to be expressed as a function of the geometrical ratio (α , $0 < \alpha < 1$) of lumen radius (r_l) to fiber radius (r_f), ratio (β) of thermal conductivities of fiber (K_f) to matrix (K_m), and fiber volume fraction (V_f). The analytical results showed that, as the V_f increases, K changes in the following two styles: K increases when α is smaller than a critical value α_c and K decreases when α is larger than α_c . The critical value α_c depends only on the value of β , in addition a smaller value of β leads to a smaller value of α_c . Transverse thermal conductivity of unidirectional green composites is significantly affected by lumen size ratio α . It is concluded that the green composites having better transverse thermal insulation characteristics can be designed by choosing the natural fibers with larger lumen.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently natural fibers have been a subject of interest in the composites due to their characteristic properties such as good biodegradability, low density, and high specific properties [1–3]. Many scientist and engineers have been trying to make high-strength green composites reinforced with natural fibers. Not only mechanical performance, but also thermal properties of natural fiber composites have been considered as a potential function. Because most natural fibers have an internal hollow microstructure, the design of composites with a good thermal insulation property by using natural fiber and polymer will be of great value. In the last few years, therefore many works have been started on thermal conductivity of natural fiber composites [4–8].

The thermal properties of natural fiber-reinforced composites are thought to be governed by many different parameters such as the values of thermal conductivity for each constituent materials, internal microstructure of the natural fibers, fiber volume content, and fiber arrangement. In the case of conventional polymer composites, their reinforcing phase is usually a solid fiber. Thus the thermal conductivity of the conventional unidirectional polymer composites is only thermal conductivity values and fiber volume content. However in the case of green composites, the air in the lumen acts as a good heat barrier media. Hence there is a possibility to obtain heat insulating polymer composites with high-strength. These properties are never achieved in the conventional composites such as glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) or carbon fiber-reinforced plastics (CFRP).

The present study was carried out to investigate thermal insulation characteristics of green composites as a function of three characteristic values of natural fiber, namely (a) the ratio of lumen's

radius to fiber's radius, (b) the ratio of thermal conductivity of natural fiber to that of matrix resin, and (c) fiber volume content. First we will propose a simplified composite unit cell model for the evaluation of thermal conductivity of model composite reinforced by a hollow fiber; then describe the details of the analytical scheme, and finally demonstrate some representative data indicating the effects of the above factors on the transverse thermal conductivity of the green composites.

2 THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF COMPOSITE UNIT CELL MODEL

An example of cross-sectional view of a natural fiber (Manila hemp fiber) is presented in Fig. 1, showing that macroscopic one fiber is composed of a number of single fibers, and each single fiber has a lumen (appeared as a black hole) in the fiber. It is well known that this lumen size is different species by species, namely some kinds of natural fibers have a very large lumen.

Figure 1: Lumens in hemp fiber bundle [11].

Figure 2: An example of finite element model for composite unit cell model with 19 lumens ($N=19$) [11].

The transverse heat conducting problem of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites can be modeled as shown in Fig. 2. In this model, T_H and T_L are surface temperatures of the unit cell, and $T_H > T_L$. The finite element model used in this model comprises about 18,500 four-node elements with less or more elements depending upon geometric parameters. The heat flux loaded on the two side faces, Q_i and Q_o ($Q = Q_i = -Q_o > 0$), are obtained after the simulation, and then substituted into Eq. (1) to obtain the effective thermal conductivity K_e :

$$K_e = QL / (T_H - T_L) / H = Q / (T_H - T_L) \quad (1)$$

In order to examine the effect of total volume of lumens on the effective thermal conductivity, the number of lumen in the composite unit cell model was reduced with keeping the total volume of lumens constant. The calculated effective thermal conductivity, K_e , for all the models is evaluated by relative deviation defined as follows:

$$D_k = (K_e - K_1) / K_1 \times 100 (\%), \quad (2)$$

where K_1 is the thermal conductivity of the composite unit cell model with one lumen.

Figure 3 shows how the number of lumen N affects the thermal conductivity of composite unit cell model as the total volume of the lumen is kept constant. In Fig. 3, we can see that K is almost same for different number of lumen. The reason for this is that the anisotropy of composite is the most prominent for $N=2$ and becomes smaller with increasing the number of lumen involved, and that the distribution of lumens tends to be isotropy like circle, when N is large enough. Therefore, composite unit cell model with single lumen ($N=1$) can replace that with many lumens for the thermal conductivity analysis. Tai has also introduced the same results that the volume of fiber greatly affects the thermal conductivity of two phase system (fiber- or particle-reinforced composites) [9, 10].

Figure 3: Variation of D_k with number of lumens [11].

3 EFFECTS OF FIBER PROPERTIS

Other important factors affecting the thermal conductivity of the green composites are thermal conductivity values of fiber and resin, lumen size, and fiber content. In order to evaluate the effects of each factors more precisely, we introduced two new factors; the ratio of thermal conductivity of fiber to matrix, $\beta = K_f / K_m$ and the ratio of lumen radius and fiber radius, $\alpha = r_l / r_f$. In addition, dimensionless thermal conductivity K / K_m was also introduced; where K , K_f and K_m are thermal conductivity of composites, fiber and matrix, respectively, r_l and r_f are radius of lumen and that of fiber.

Figure 4 represents the dimensionless transverse thermal conductivities, K / K_m , versus fiber volume content as a function of lumen size ratio α . It can be seen that thermal conductivity, K / K_m , shows great difference in trend of changing with fiber content when α varies from 0 to 1. In Fig. 4(a), i.e. $\beta = 0.5 < 1$, K / K_m decreases with increasing V_f for any value of α , because of much lower thermal conductivity of fiber than matrix. Therefore, it is easy to understand that the effective transverse thermal conductivity of unidirectional Manila hemp fiber-PLA composite [12] decreases with increasing volume fraction of Manila hemp fiber because of $\beta = 0.19 \text{ [W/(mK)]} / 0.425 \text{ [W/(mK)]} = 0.45 < 1$. In contrast, in Figs. 4(b)–(d), i.e. $\beta > 1$, K / K_m shows an increasing trend at lower value $\alpha = 0.1, 0.3$, and 0.5 , however shows a decreasing trend at higher value $\alpha = 0.7$, and 0.9 . It should be noted that larger lumen leads to lower effective transverse thermal conductivity but smaller lumen causes higher effective transverse thermal conductivity. This is consistent with the physical situation. It means that unidirectional hollow fiber-reinforced composite materials with large lumen content will have a good thermal insulation property. On the contrary, the composite with large thermal conduction results from the fiber with smaller lumen.

Figure 4: The variation of dimensionless thermal conductivity, K/K_m with fiber volume content, V_f ; (a) $\beta = 0.5$, (b) $\beta = 5$, (c) $\beta = 10$, and (d) $\beta = 1000$ [13].

From Fig. 4(c), it can be seen that the dimensionless thermal conductivity is almost constant in the case of $\alpha=0.7$, and that the thermal conductivity increases with increasing fiber volume fraction when α is smaller than critical value of α_c ; namely α_c value for this case is approximately 0.7. On the other hand, the dimensionless thermal conductivity decreases with increasing fiber volume content when α is larger than α_c . Therefore this critical value of α_c becomes an important index for choosing natural fiber to obtain the green composites with better thermal insulation property.

4 CONCLUSIONS

1. The transverse thermal conductivity of unit cell model for the composites reinforced with many lumens is same as that for the composites reinforced with one lumen having the same lumen volume.
2. The dimensionless effective transverse thermal conductivity of natural fiber is affected by the geometrical ratio of the lumen; $\alpha = r_l/r_f$, thermal conductivity ratio; $\beta = K_f/K_m$, and fiber volume fraction V_f .
3. The transverse thermal conductivity of green composites decreases with increasing fiber volume content when the lumen size is larger than the critical α value, α_c .

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) KAKENHI Grant Number 25289243.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Nabi and J. P. Jog, *Advances in Polymer Technology*, **18**, 1999, pp. 351–363.
- [2] A. K. Bledzki and J. Gassan, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **24**, 1999, pp. 221–274.
- [3] H. Takagi and Y. Ichihara, *JSME International Journal, Series A*, **47**, 2004, pp. 551–555.
- [4] H. Takagi, S. Kako, K. Kusano, and A. Ousaka, *Advanced Composite Materials*, **16**, 2007, pp. 377–384.
- [5] X. Li, L. G. Tabil, I. N. Oguocha, and S. Panigrahi, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 1753–1758.
- [6] M. R. Wang, J. H. He, J. Y. Yu, and N. Pan, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, **46**, 2007, pp. 848–855.
- [7] S. W. Kim, S. H. Lee, J. S. Kang, and K. H. Kang, *International Journal of Thermophysics*, **27**, 2006, pp. 1873–1881.
- [8] T. Behzad and M. Sain, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, **47**, 2007, pp. 977–983.
- [9] H. Tai, *Journal of Composite Technology Research*, **18**, 1996, pp. 221–227.
- [10] H. Tai, *International Journal of Thermophysics*, **19**, 1998, pp. 1485–1492.
- [11] K. Liu, H. Takagi, and Z. Yang, *Materials & Design*, **32**, 2011, pp. 4586–4589.
- [12] H. Takagi and Y. Gennai, *Proceedings of the 58th JSMS Annual Meetings*, 2009, pp. 319–320.
- [13] K. Liu, H. Takagi, R. Osugi, and Z. Yang, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 633–639.